

FORMATION OF STUDENTS' COMPETENCE TO UNDERSTAND HISTORICAL REALITY AND LOGICAL EXPLANATION AS A SOCIAL AND PEDAGOGICAL TASK

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8395214>

Abstract. *In this article, students will be able to understand the historical reality and explain it logically, to develop historical thinking, to educate them as well-rounded individuals with intellectual potential, to develop the competence of being able to explain logically coherently, in order to build a socially just society of pedagogical conditions for students to become professionals. the development of adulthood through pedagogical and psychological means of influence is highlighted.*

Keywords: *education, youth, socialization, historical reality, logical consistency, creative, mature, individuality, mechanism, reform, initiative, volunteering, divergent thinking, competence, intellectual, motivational, moral education, forecasting, integration.*

On the basis of the reforms carried out in the field of education in the Republic of Uzbekistan, the formation of the competence of young people to understand the historical reality and explain it logically, which is the country's today and tomorrow, is being put forward as an important issue. The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan touched upon the issue of raising mature young people who can think logically: in his address to the Oliy Majlis on December 29, 2020, he said: "The solution is for the young generation to grow up healthy and mature, who will ensure its future in the development of society. takes place. For this reason, we rely on our young people who are mature in all aspects, who have thoroughly mastered modern knowledge and skills, are determined and enterprising, to further increase the scope and effectiveness of our reforms. It is important to mature as a person with high logical thinking [1].

One of the main rules of the competence approach in education is the understanding of competence as a subjective quality of a person. This is the collective nature of educational activities and the assimilation of knowledge through strict social factors, the development of skills and competencies in students that depend on the subjective motives of studying, attitude to the subject of study, education it is manifested in pedagogical conditions, taking into account the abilities and experience of the recipient. For this reason, it is considered an urgent issue to consider the work being researched in scientific research in recent years, the formation of the competence to understand historical reality and explain it logically as a factor affecting the social qualities of students in the educational system.

In the development of individual qualities in the student, we first consider the relation to the historical reality as a social pedagogical necessity: based on the ancient Chinese pedagogical and moral views, ideas about the importance of individual characteristics were put forward to the learner, and the norms and principles of education knowledge was imparted through the first

generalized ideas about These ideas formed the basis of further development of pedagogical ideas and practice. This tradition began to be used in practice for the first time in the ancient times, when the views on the “individual approach” were accepted in society. In the Renaissance and the New Century, the idea of an approach to individual historical reality began to be expressed in all spheres of social life and increased attention to individual self-awareness, understanding, and individual life of a person.

From the point of view of the factors influencing the ability to understand the historical reality and explain it logically, we express it in the educational system through an individual historical approach, which consists in activating social projects with a pedagogical-psychological process that is relevant for the subject. We understand it as the activity of using methods and tools in pedagogical conditions that ensure the unique characteristics of the educational process. Factors reflecting the historical reality affecting the educational process also play an important role.

As one of the main factors of the development of education and science during today's reforms, the educational requirements for the history teacher to develop the qualities of understanding the historical reality and being able to explain it in a logical consistency at the stage of the development of the society, with significant changes in the content of the history Development of theoretical and methodological approaches to the study of the past in the development of the competence of the history teacher during the educational process, and the possibility of analyzing historical sources and the works of local and foreign historians in the training of science specialists are of particular importance in the development of society. Because, while studying historical sources, the question of studying one's own research in connection with the development of modern advanced pedagogical and information technologies occupies a special place.

Through the development of practical-cognitive competencies of students studying in higher education institutions, the thinking of future specialists, independent work on themselves, development of creative-creative qualities in the process of preparation for education and in the process of education and training in the field of science in students Pedagogical and psychological aspects are important for the development of cognitive competence. Research conducted by scientists has paid special attention to the issues of elucidating the pedagogical and psychological aspects of the development of practical-cognitive competence in future informatics teachers.

N.A.Muslimov emphasized that “competence is the ability to use knowledge, skills and personal qualities for successful activity in a certain field”[2].

Dj.Patrick, P.White, as well as Canadian pedagogues A.Sears and E.Hughes stated that one of the most important factors in the development of social competences is the desire to support and develop democracy, which is achieved through qualities that help the development of civil society [3].

In the opinions of Mr.Walo Hutmasher [19], the concept of "competence" is in the process of discussions as a term that is not clearly defined until it enters the content of the concepts of “knowledge”, “competence”, ”ability”, “skill”. Competency approach in scientist education

It is interpreted in 5 aspects. That is, it interprets it into sociological, intercultural, communicative, technological, cognitive aspects [4].

Therefore, in order to increase the meaning of the concept of “competence”, we will pay special attention to the definition of this term, its general and specific features. When this concept is translated from the Latin language, “sompentia” can be expressed as a concept that means a

number of issues that a person knows well, has knowledge and experience. The difference between the concept of "competency" and the pedagogical concepts is that it occupies an important place in the structure of real-life objective concepts based on it. The misunderstandings and ambiguities surrounding the concept of "competence" originate from the objectivist perspective, which is ready to accept a single and true definition of competence. This problem is solved from the point of view of the constructive approach, which assumes the existence of several definitions. In this approach, the criterion of the adequacy of the concept is the boundaries of the semantic field, which have meaning in the context in which the definition is used.

In our view, the formation of the competence of history teachers to understand historical reality and explain it logically is a pedagogical problem:

firstly, the competence to understand the historical reality and explain it in a logical consistency, by creating an atmosphere of creativity in the students during the educational process, brings out the work motives and opportunities of the students;

secondly, forming the competence to understand the historical reality and explain it logically has an external motivational effect on the group team in bringing out the qualities of creativity;

therefore, the ability to understand the historical reality and explain it in a logical consistency is necessary for the students to achieve the activity skills set as a goal, to work on the basis of independent historical creative activity skills, and to develop the necessary skills and research abilities in the development of personal qualities. the qualities of realizing educational opportunities are currently considered as an urgent problem.

Development of personal-pedagogical qualities of history teachers in forming the competence to understand the historical reality and explain it logically, the analysis of modern conceptual educational approaches to the design and implementation of the educational process, the existence of a number of shortcomings in the new stage showed:

the theoretical and practical foundations of the active involvement of history teachers in the process of education in understanding the historical reality and explaining it in a logical consistency are not sufficiently developed;

the dynamics of increasing the level of development of teachers' ability to understand historical reality and explain it logically in the educational process has not been sufficiently developed;

the problem of choosing the content of special courses as one of the forms of scientific research activity in the history teacher's ability to understand the historical reality and explain it in logical consistency has not been solved, in which special course programs were formed without taking into account new achievements in the field of history;

it should also be noted that innovative educational forms and interactive methods of teaching aimed at forming the research competence of history teachers are not fully used.

As a result of the knowledge acquired by history specialists in the formation of the competence to understand the historical reality and explain it in a logical consistency, the following skills develop:

a special place is given to the formation of knowledge, skills, qualifications, experience of practical activity, competence in the training of competitive qualified personnel in the society;

It is important to distinguish between the ability to understand the historical reality within the science and to explain it logically in the context of science in continuing higher education in the master's degree in the specialty chosen within the field of undergraduate education.

Schelling, one of the foreign scientists, dwells on the issues of understanding the historical reality and the ability to explain it logically. creates in a state of physicality, unconsciousness, the process still takes place in the state of human subjectivity and therefore depends on his freedom. According to Schelling, the work of an artist and a philosopher represents the highest form of human activity.

Husserl views creativity as a science, emphasizes intellectual thinking, and believes that as a result of it, the level of intelligent and wise man will be reached [5]. Understanding the historical reality and being able to explain it logically is the creativity of a person, creative thinking, creative activity, scientific and creative views, which are also discussed in the works of local and foreign psychologists.

In psychology, creativity is studied mainly as a psychological process of new thinking and as a set of personal qualities that ensure that a person is involved in this process. In the scientific literature, the problem of “creative activity” is more developed. According to L.S.Vygotsky's definition, “we consider creative activity whether it is an object of the external world created in creative activity, or whether it is a certain structure of the mind or feeling that lives and is determined only by the person himself. Regardless, we understand the creative activity of a person” [6].

According to S.L.Rubinstein, the sudden opening of great discoveries cannot be denied, but their source is not “intuition”, it is not an effortless, characteristic “sudden awakening of consciousness”. This phenomenon only reflects a specific critical (critical) point that is clearly visible, separating an unresolved issue from a resolved one. The sudden, “intuitive” nature of creative activity is reflected when the hypothetical solution is more obvious than the ways and methods leading to it. It is a kind of anticipation or anticipation of the results of the mental work that must be done. The thinking activity of a scientist is usually systematically expressed, and the expectation itself is the product of long-term conscious work. “Creative work of a scientist is creative work” says Rubinstein [7].

A.N.Leontev in his lecture “Experience of experimental research of thinking” emphasizes the determinants of the importance of experimentation in the study of creativity and offers his own interpretation of the stages of the creative process:

- 1) finding an adequate solution principle (method);
- 2) applying it in connection with the investigation, re-changing this principle in accordance with the characteristics of the problem to be solved [8].

According to him, the first stage is the most creative part of thinking activity, the main aspect of which is that “after fruitless attempts to find a solution to the problem, a solution suddenly appears, a new idea for a solution appears. In this case, he often emphasizes the randomness of the circumstances in which such a sudden emergence of a new idea, a new principle of a solution” [8; p. 5].

From foreign countries, it was organized in Germany with an emphasis on 6 aspects of the competence approach. Therefore, they began to gradually enter the educational system in accordance with the current educational standard, and began to integrate it into the educational content based on the following competency approaches:

- Handlungskompetenz i.e. (action competence); acquires subject and subject competencies;
- Professional competence is aimed at emphasizing the formation of professional competence in students through this competence;
- Sashkompetenz (general knowledge competences) - independent thinking, creative thinking and the ability to act, research and problem solving skills are formed;
- Personal kompetenz (personal-competence) - readiness and ability to understand, analyze and evaluate the ways of development of personal abilities, requirements and boundaries in personal, work and social life, the ability to choose and implement life plans;
- Soziaekompetenz (social competences);
- Lernkompetenz (educational competences) is directed to the organization of educational competences, which are equated with meta-competencies, during the educational process.

In particular, as a result of one or another educational activity in scientific research conducted by scientists, the ability to understand historical reality and explain it logically is the acquired knowledge, skills and abilities of the student, as well as independent training in professional direction. It is appropriate to analyze the issues of orientation. Thus, the analysis of the studied scientific and pedagogical literature shows that through independent learning, the future student acquires the competence to understand the historical reality and explain it logically in connection with the independent thinking of the individual in his field of activity. formation is important.

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